

Energy shaping control of a class of underactuated mechanical systems with high-order actuator dynamics

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ABSTRACT

In this work we present some new results on energy shaping control for underactuated mechanical systems with high-order actuator dynamics. To this end, we propose an extension of the *Interconnection and damping assignment Passivity based control* methodology to account for actuator dynamics. This brings the following new results: i) a potential and kinetic energy shaping and damping assignment procedure that yields two alternative controllers; ii) a potential energy shaping and damping assignment procedure for a narrower class of underactuated mechanical systems. The proposed approach is illustrated with numerical simulations on three examples: an Acrobot system with a series elastic actuator; a soft continuum manipulator actuated by electroactive polymers; a two-mass-spring system actuated by a DC motor.

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1. Introduction

Energy shaping control offers a range of desirable features, including the physical interpretation of the control action in terms of system energy, which have made this approach a popular choice for a variety of applications. In particular, the *Interconnection and damping assignment Passivity based control* (IDA-PBC) methodology [18] involves designing the control action such that the closed-loop dynamics preserves the port-Hamiltonian structure and is characterized by a prescribed total energy. IDA-PBC controllers have been designed for a variety of systems, including fully actuated robots [23], underactuated satellites [2], unmanned surface vessels [14,20], piezoelectric beams [12], and soft robotic manipulators [7,15]. In case of underactuated systems, the controller design requires solving analytically a set of partial differential equations (PDEs), which can be a challenging task. This aspect has motivated a number of works, including a method to simplify the PDEs for mechanical systems [21], the study of kinetic energy shaping for mechanical systems [11], the algebraic solutions of the PDEs in Nunna et al. [17], and the numerical solution of the PDEs with reinforcement learning in Gheibi et al. [10]. A further line of research has investigated the effect of disturbances within IDA-

PBC, resulting in more sophisticated controllers that achieve robustification through integral actions [3] or adaptive observers [8].

Thanks to its physical interpretation in terms of system energy, the IDA-PBC methodology has proved well suited to control multi-domain systems which involve energy exchanges between different components. Notable examples include magnetic levitation systems [17], weakly-coupled electro-mechanical systems [22], and more recently mechanical systems with fluidic actuation [5,6]. In principle, the IDA-PBC methodology can be employed to account for high-order actuator dynamics within the controller design. Nevertheless, this has typically been avoided for simplicity, considering that many actuators have higher bandwidth compared to the corresponding mechanical sub-systems [19]. In general, accounting for the actuator dynamics results in a system which is not input affine hence potentially complicating the controller design. Notable results in this direction include IDA-PBC designs for mechanical systems that account for the first-order dynamics of electric motors in Gandarilla et al. [9] and Wang et al. [26]. In addition, an energy shaping controller has been designed for a soft continuum manipulator actuated by electroactive polymers in Mattioni et al. [15]. Finally, in our recent work [5], we have proposed an IDA-PBC implementation for underactuated mechanical systems with fluidic actuation, which accounts for the pressure dynamics of the fluid, either pneumatic or hydraulic. In summary, the former controllers are either specific to a system or to a type of actuator, thus they are not directly applicable to different actuation strategies characterized by high-order dynamics.

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This work investigates the energy shaping control for underactuated mechanical system with high-order actuator dynamics and presents the following new results.

- An energy shaping and damping assignment procedure that builds upon the IDA-PBC methodology preserving the port-Hamiltonian structure, and which yields two alternative controllers. This approach is feasible for a class of systems defined by a clear set of conditions. In addition, a potential shaping procedure is detailed for a narrower class of underactuated mechanical systems.
- Numerical simulations for three illustrative case studies: an Acrobot system with a series elastic actuator; a soft continuum manipulator actuated by electroactive polymers; a two-mass-spring system actuated by a DC motor.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: a brief overview of the IDA-PBC methodology is provided in Section 2 for completeness; the definition of the system class is given in Section 3; two controller design procedures for kinetic and potential energy shaping are detailed in Section 4; a controller design procedure for potential energy shaping is discussed in Section 5; illustrative examples are presented in Section 6; concluding remarks are given in Section 7.

2. Overview of IDA-PBC

The dynamics of an underactuated mechanical system with n degrees-of-freedom (DOFs) and direct actuation $u \in \mathbb{R}^m$ through the input matrix $G(q) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, where $\text{rank}(G) = m < n$ for all $q \in \mathbb{R}^n$, is described in port-Hamiltonian form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{q} \\ \dot{p} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I \\ -I & -D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \nabla_q H \\ \nabla_p H \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ G \end{bmatrix} u, \quad y = G^T \nabla_p H, \quad (1)$$

where $D = D^T \geq 0$ is the damping matrix, and the total mechanical energy is

$$H(q, p) = \Omega + \frac{1}{2} p^T M^{-1} p, \quad (2)$$

characterized by the inertia matrix $M(q) = M(q)^T > 0$, and the potential energy $\Omega(q)$. The system states are the position $q \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and the momenta $p = M\dot{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The remaining terms in (1) are the identity matrix I , the vector of partial derivatives of H in q , $\nabla_q H$, and the vector of partial derivatives of H in p , $\nabla_p H$. The control aim corresponds to stabilizing the equilibrium $(q, p) = (q^*, 0)$, and it is achieved with the IDA-PBC control law [18]

$$u = G^\dagger (\nabla_q H - M_d M^{-1} \nabla_q H_d + J_2 \nabla_p H_d) - k_v G^T \nabla_p H_d, \quad (3)$$

where $G^\dagger = (G^T G)^{-1} G^T$. The resulting closed-loop dynamics is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{q} \\ \dot{p} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & M^{-1} M_d \\ -M_d M^{-1} & J_2 - (G k_v G^T + D M^{-1} M_d) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \nabla_q H_d \\ \nabla_p H_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $H_d = \Omega_d + \frac{1}{2} p^T M_d^{-1} p$. The design parameters in (4) are the potential energy Ω_d , the inertia matrix $M_d = M_d^T > 0$, the free matrix $J_2 = -J_2^T$, and the constant matrix $k_v = k_v^T > 0$. To achieve the regulation goal, the potential energy Ω_d should admit a strict global minimizer in q^* hence verifying the conditions $\nabla_q \Omega_d(q^*) = 0$ and $\nabla_q^2 \Omega_d(q^*) > 0$. In addition, M_d and Ω_d should verify for all $(q, p) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ the PDEs

$$G^\perp (\nabla_q (p^T M^{-1} p) - M_d M^{-1} \nabla_q (p^T M_d^{-1} p) + 2J_2 M_d^{-1} p) = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$G^\perp (\nabla_q \Omega - M_d M^{-1} \nabla_q \Omega_d) = 0, \quad (6)$$

where G^\perp is such that $G^\perp G = 0$ and $\text{rank}(G^\perp) = n - m$. Computing the time derivative of H_d along the trajectories of the closed-loop

system (4) yields

$$\dot{H}_d = -\nabla_p H_d^T \left(G k_v G^T + \frac{1}{2} (D M^{-1} M_d) + \frac{1}{2} (D M^{-1} M_d)^T \right) \nabla_p H_d \leq 0. \quad (7)$$

Thus the equilibrium $(q, p) = (q^*, 0)$ is asymptotically stable if $(G k_v G^T + \frac{1}{2} (D M^{-1} M_d) + \frac{1}{2} (D M^{-1} M_d)^T) \geq 0$ and the output $y = G^T \nabla_p H_d$ is detectable [18].

3. System class definition

Consider the underactuated mechanical system defined by (1) and (2) where the actuator dynamics has order $s \geq 1$. The complete system dynamics in port-Hamiltonian form is thus

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{q} \\ \dot{p} \\ \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \dot{x}_s \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 0 & I & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -I & -D & \mathcal{F}_{23} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -\mathcal{F}_{23}^T & -\mathcal{R}_{33} & \mathcal{F}_{34} & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\mathcal{R}_{34}^T & -\mathcal{R}_{44} & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & -\mathcal{R}_{s+2,s+2} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathcal{F}} \begin{bmatrix} \nabla_q W \\ \nabla_p W \\ \nabla_{x_1} W \\ \nabla_{x_2} W \\ \vdots \\ \nabla_{x_s} W \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ G_0 \end{bmatrix} u, \quad (8)$$

where $W = \Omega + \frac{1}{2} p^T M^{-1} p + \sum_{j=1}^s E_j$ and $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}_0 - \mathcal{R}_0$ with $\mathcal{F}_0 = -\mathcal{F}_0^T$, $\mathcal{R}_0 = \mathcal{R}_0^T = \text{diag}(\mathcal{R}_{ii})$. The generic element of \mathcal{F} on row i and column j is indicated with \mathcal{F}_{ij} , thus $\mathcal{F}_{ji} = -\mathcal{F}_{ij}$ for all $i \neq j$. In summary, the total energy W comprises the mechanical energy $H = \Omega + \frac{1}{2} p^T M^{-1} p$, while the remaining terms E_j represent the energy of the actuators. The system states are $x = (q, p, x_1, \dots, x_s)$ with $q \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $p \in \mathbb{R}^n$ referring to the mechanical system (1), and $(x_1, \dots, x_s) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times s}$ referring to the actuator, and the new input matrix is $G_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$. In summary, system (8) is an extension of system (1) obtained by including the dynamics of the actuators. The class of systems considered in this work is defined by the following assumptions.

Assumption 1. The PDEs (5) and (6) for system (1) with direct actuation are solvable analytically, Ω_d is positive definite, $q^* = \text{argmin}(\Omega_d)$, and either $D_d = G k_v G^T + \frac{1}{2} (D M^{-1} M_d) + \frac{1}{2} (D M^{-1} M_d)^T > 0$, or $y = G^T M_d^{-1} p$ is detectable if $D = 0$. Finally, all model parameters are exactly known and all system states are measurable.

Assumption 2. The interconnection matrix \mathcal{F} in (8) has off-diagonal elements $\mathcal{F}_{ij} = 0$ if $j > i + 1$ and either $\text{rank}(\mathcal{F}_{ij}) = m$ if $j = i + 1$ or $\nabla_{x_j} (\mathcal{F}_{j+1,1}^T \nabla_q W + \mathcal{F}_{j+1,2} \nabla_p W) \neq 0$, while the diagonal terms are $\mathcal{R}_{ii} \geq 0$.

Assumption 3. The energy of the actuators is such that $\nabla_{x_j} E_i = 0$ if $j > i$ and $\nabla_{x_j} E_j \neq 0$. Finally, G_0 is full rank for all (q, p, x_1, \dots, x_s) .

Remark 1. The first assumption defines the class of systems for which the IDA-PBC methodology is applicable, according to Ortega et al. [18]. The analytical solvability of the PDEs is a research topic in itself [17], thus it is not investigated further. Nevertheless, the PDEs (5) and (6) are solvable analytically for several canonical examples including, the disk-on-disk [3], the inertia-wheel-pendulum [21], the ball-on-beam [18], and the Acrobot [16], which is illustrated in Section 6. If $s = 0$ the conditions of

Assumptions 2 and **3** are verified, that is $\mathcal{F}_{12} = I \neq 0$, $\mathcal{R}_{22} = D \geq 0$ and $\nabla_p \Omega = 0$, $\nabla_q^2 \Omega \neq 0$, $\nabla_p^2 (\frac{1}{2} p^T M^{-1} p) = M^{-1} \neq 0$. In general, **Assumptions 2** and **3** imply that the actuator dynamics in (8) is in strict-feedback form, with the key difference that the mechanical sub-system (1) is underactuated. As a result, the controller design cannot be performed with the same backstepping approach used for fully actuated systems [13]. In addition, employing a backstepping design that builds upon the IDA-PBC controller (3) would not preserve the port-Hamiltonian structure in closed loop [5,6]. Note finally that, while systems (8) is not directly actuated, the input matrix G is still relevant since it defines the states affected by the actuator dynamics.

4. Potential and kinetic energy shaping

The aim of this work is to account for high-order actuator dynamics by building upon the IDA-PBC methodology [18] in a modular fashion and by preserving the port-Hamiltonian structure of the system in closed loop. To this end we propose a controller design procedure that preserves the PDEs (5) and (6) characterizing system (1). The main idea behind the controller design is to: i) express the actuator dynamics in port-Hamiltonian form (8); ii) define a corresponding closed-loop dynamics compatibly with the regulation goal; iii) construct a control law that ensures matching between open-loop and closed-loop dynamics thus extending our work [5] to generic high-order actuator dynamics.

4.1. First controller design

The control law for system (8) is designed such that the closed-loop dynamics is port-Hamiltonian, that is

$$\dot{x} = [\mathcal{F}'] [\nabla_x W_d], \tag{9}$$

where $\mathcal{F}' = \mathcal{F}^* - \mathcal{R}^*$ with $\mathcal{F}^* = -\mathcal{F}^{*T}$ and $\mathcal{R}^* = \mathcal{R}^{*T} \geq 0$, the total energy is $W_d = H_d + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^s \zeta_k^T \zeta_k$, with $H_d = \Omega_d + \frac{1}{2} p^T M_d^{-1} p$ characterizing the mechanical sub-system, and $\zeta_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are defined as

$$\zeta_k = \begin{cases} G^\dagger (-\nabla_q W + \mathcal{F}_{23} \nabla_{x_1} W + M_d M^{-1} \nabla_q H_d + (Gk_v G^T - J_2) \nabla_p H_d), & k = 1 \\ -\mathcal{F}_{2,k+1}^T \nabla_p W - \sum_{j=1}^k \mathcal{F}_{j+2,k+1}^T \nabla_{x_j} W + \mathcal{F}_{1,k+1}^T (\nabla_q H_d + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (\nabla_q \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i) \\ + \mathcal{F}_{2,k+1}^T (\nabla_p H_d + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (\nabla_p \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i) + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \mathcal{F}_{j+2,k+1}^T (\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i), & k > 1, \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

to ensure matching between (8) and (9) for the states (x_1, \dots, x_s) . The elements of \mathcal{F}' on or above the diagonal (i.e., \mathcal{F}'_{kj} on row k and column $j \geq k$), are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}'_{11} &= 0, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{12} = M^{-1} M_d, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{22} = -DM^{-1} M_d - Gk_v G^T + J_2, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{23} &= G \left(1 + G^\dagger \mathcal{F}_{12}^T \nabla_q \zeta_1 - G^\dagger \mathcal{F}'_{22} \nabla_p \zeta_1 \right) (\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^{-1} + G^{\perp T} \left(G^\otimes \mathcal{F}_{12}^T \nabla_q \zeta_1 - G^\otimes \mathcal{F}'_{22} \nabla_p \zeta_1 \right) (\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^{-1}, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{kj} &= \begin{cases} \left(1 + \mathcal{F}_{1k}^T \nabla_q \zeta_{j-2} + \mathcal{F}_{2k}^T \nabla_p \zeta_{j-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{j-1} (\mathcal{F}_{ik}^T \nabla_{x_{i-2}} \zeta_{j-2}) \right) (\nabla_{x_{j-2}} \zeta_{j-2})^{-1} & j = k + 1 > 3 \\ \left(\mathcal{F}_{1k}^T \nabla_q \zeta_{j-2} + \mathcal{F}_{2k}^T \nabla_p \zeta_{j-2} + \sum_{i=3}^{j-1} (\mathcal{F}_{ik}^T \nabla_{x_{i-2}} \zeta_{j-2}) \right) (\nabla_{x_{j-2}} \zeta_{j-2})^{-1} & j > k + 1, \\ -K_{j-2} < 0 & j = k > 2, \end{cases} \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where $G^\otimes = (G^\perp G^{\perp T})^{-1} G^\perp$, K_{j-2} are tuning parameters, while Ω_d, M_d and J_2 are computed by solving the PDEs (5) and (6) that characterize system (1). It follows from (10) that $\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1 = G^\dagger \mathcal{F}_{23} \nabla_{x_1} E_1$, where $\text{rank}(\mathcal{F}_{23}) = m$ (see **Assumption 2**) and $\nabla_{x_1} E_1 \neq 0$ (see **Assumption 3**) hence $\text{rank}(\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1) = m$. The same applies to $\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j$. The control input that yields the closed-loop dynamics (9) is

$$u = G_0^{-1} \left(\mathcal{F}_{1,s+2}^T \nabla_q W + \mathcal{F}_{2,s+2}^T \nabla_p W + \sum_{j=1}^s \mathcal{F}_{j+2,s+2}^T \nabla_{x_j} W - \mathcal{F}_{1,s+2}^T \nabla_q W_d - \mathcal{F}_{2,s+2}^T \nabla_p W_d - \sum_{j=1}^s \mathcal{F}_{j+2,s+2}^T \nabla_{x_j} W_d \right). \tag{12}$$

It follows from (10), (11) that ζ_k and \mathcal{F}'_{kj} are interdependent, thus they cannot be computed simultaneously and independently of each other. Therefore, the control law is constructed by employing the following design procedure.

1. Compute the expressions of Ω_d, M_d and J_2 by solving the PDEs (5) and (6) for the mechanical sub-system (1).
2. Compute $\mathcal{F}'_{12}, \mathcal{F}'_{22}$ and the diagonal terms \mathcal{F}'_{jj} from (11).
3. Compute ζ_1 from (10) and subsequently compute $\mathcal{F}'_{13}, \mathcal{F}'_{23}$ from (11).
4. Compute ζ_2 from (10) and subsequently compute $\mathcal{F}'_{14}, \mathcal{F}'_{24}, \mathcal{F}'_{34}$ from (11).
5. Compute ζ_k from (10) and subsequently compute $\mathcal{F}'_{1,k+2}, \mathcal{F}'_{2,k+2}, \dots, \mathcal{F}'_{k+1,k+2}$ from (11) for all subsequent $k \leq s$.
6. Compute the control input from (12).

Proposition 1. Consider system (8) with **Assumptions 1–3** and with the control law (12). Then the closed-loop system is given by (9), the matrix \mathcal{F}' is given by (11), and ζ_k is given by (10).

Proof. Equating the first rows in (8) and (9) yields

$$\begin{aligned} M^{-1} p &= M^{-1} M_d \left(M_d^{-1} p + \sum_{k=1}^s (\nabla_p \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k \right) \\ &+ \sum_{j=1}^s \left(\mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2} \sum_{k=j}^s (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k \right). \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Defining $\mathcal{F}'_{1,s+2}$ according to (11), that is

$$\mathcal{F}'_{1,s+2} = - \left(\mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_p \zeta_s + \sum_{j=1}^{s-1} (\mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2} \nabla_{x_j} \zeta_s) \right) (\nabla_{x_s} \zeta_s)^{-1},$$

and substituting in (13) cancels ζ_s . Similarly, substituting $\mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2}$ with $j > 2$ cancels ζ_j until (13) yields the identity.

Equating the second rows in (8) and (9) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\nabla_q W - DM^{-1}p + \mathcal{F}_{23}\nabla_{x_1}W = \\
 & -\mathcal{F}'_{12}\left(\nabla_q H_d + \sum_{k=1}^s(\nabla_q \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right) + \mathcal{F}'_{22}\left(M_d^{-1}p + \sum_{k=1}^s(\nabla_p \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right) \\
 & + \sum_{j=1}^s\left(\mathcal{F}'_{2,j+2}\sum_{k=j}^s(\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right). \tag{14}
 \end{aligned}$$

Defining $\mathcal{F}'_{2,j+2}$ with $j > 1$ according to (11) and substituting it in (14) cancels ζ_j for all $j > 1$. Substituting \mathcal{F}'_{22} while simplifying common terms, and pre-multiplying both sides of (14) by G^\otimes gives the matching conditions [5]

$$\begin{aligned}
 G^\otimes(-\nabla_q H + \mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_q H_d - J_2 M_d^{-1}p) = \\
 G^\otimes(-\mathcal{F}'_{12}(\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{22}(\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{23}(\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1), \tag{15}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the left side of the equal corresponds to the sum of the PDEs (5) and (6) (solvable analytically by hypothesis according to Assumption 1). Thus PDEs (5) and (6) are preserved as well as their analytical solutions Ω_d, M_d and J_2 . Note that $\mathcal{F}_{23}\nabla_{x_1}W$ is not part of (15), since it only affects the actuated states of the mechanical system (i.e., the actuator dynamics enters the system through the matrix G). Pre-multiplying both sides of (14) by G^\dagger yields instead

$$\begin{aligned}
 G^\dagger(-\nabla_q W + \mathcal{F}_{23}\nabla_{x_1}W + \mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_q H_d + (Gk_v G^T - J_2)M_d^{-1}p) = \\
 G^\dagger(-\mathcal{F}'_{12}(\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{22}(\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{23}(\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1), \tag{16}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the terms to the left of the equal correspond to ζ_1 in (10). Note that $\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_1 = 0$ for all $j > 1$. Thus, defining \mathcal{F}'_{23} according to (11) solves both (15) and (16).

Equating the third rows in (8) and (9) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\mathcal{F}'_{23}\nabla_p W - \mathcal{F}_{33}\nabla_{x_1}W + \mathcal{F}_{34}\nabla_{x_2}W = \\
 & -\mathcal{F}'_{13}\left(\nabla_q H_d + \sum_{k=1}^s(\nabla_q \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right) - \mathcal{F}'_{23}\left(M_d^{-1}p + \sum_{k=1}^s(\nabla_p \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right) \\
 & + \sum_{j=1}^s\left(\mathcal{F}'_{3,j+2}\sum_{k=j}^s(\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right). \tag{17}
 \end{aligned}$$

Defining $\mathcal{F}'_{3,j+2}$ with $j > 2$ according to (11) and substituting it in (17) cancels ζ_j for all $j > 2$ yielding

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\mathcal{F}'_{23}\nabla_p W - \mathcal{F}_{33}\nabla_{x_1}W + \mathcal{F}_{34}\nabla_{x_2}W \\
 & + \mathcal{F}'_{13}(\nabla_q H_d + (\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) + \mathcal{F}'_{23}(M_d^{-1}p + (\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) \\
 & - \mathcal{F}'_{33}((\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) = \\
 & -\mathcal{F}'_{13}((\nabla_q \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2) - \mathcal{F}'_{23}((\nabla_p \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2) \\
 & + \mathcal{F}'_{33}(\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{34}(\nabla_{x_2} \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2. \tag{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

The terms to the left of the equal correspond to ζ_2 , where $\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_2 = 0$ for all $j > 2$. Thus (18) is verified by defining \mathcal{F}'_{34} as in (11), that is

$$\mathcal{F}'_{34} = (1 + \mathcal{F}'_{13}\nabla_q \zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{23}\nabla_p \zeta_2 - \mathcal{F}'_{33}\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_2)(\nabla_{x_2} \zeta_2)^{-1}$$

Matching for the remaining states x_j with $j < s$ is achieved in the same fashion and is omitted for conciseness.

Equating the last rows in (8) and (9) yields finally

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\mathcal{F}'_{1,s+2}\nabla_q W - \mathcal{F}'_{2,s+2}\nabla_p W - \sum_{j=1}^s \mathcal{F}'_{j+2,s+2}\nabla_{x_j}W + G_0 u = \\
 & -\mathcal{F}'_{1,s+2}\left(\nabla_q H_d + \sum_{k=1}^s(\nabla_q \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\mathcal{F}'_{2,s+2}\left(M_d^{-1}p + \sum_{k=1}^s(\nabla_p \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right) \\
 & - \sum_{j=1}^s\left(\mathcal{F}'_{j+2,s+2}\sum_{k=j}^s(\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k\right). \tag{19}
 \end{aligned}$$

Computing u from (19) yields (12) concluding the proof. \square

Remark 2. In summary, the proposed design procedure results in the same PDEs as the traditional IDA-PBC [18]. It follows from Assumptions 2 and 3 that $\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_i = 0, \forall j > i$ and that $\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j \neq 0$, thus $\mathcal{F}'_{k,j} \in \mathcal{L}^\infty$. If the terms $\mathcal{F}_{j,j+1}$ are constant, Assumption 2 is verified provided that $\nabla_{x_j}^2 E_j \neq 0, \forall j$. If instead Assumptions 2 and 3 are not verified, that is for instance $\mathcal{F}_{14}\nabla_{x_2}W \neq 0$, then it follows from (16) that ζ_1 would depend also on x_2 . Consequently, choosing \mathcal{F}'_{13} to verify (13) would yield

$$\mathcal{F}'_{13} = -(\mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_p \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{14}\nabla_{x_2} \zeta_1)(\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^{-1},$$

which also contains \mathcal{F}'_{14} . However, it follows from (11) that \mathcal{F}'_{14} depends on \mathcal{F}'_{13} thus the design procedure outlined in Proposition 1 would not be feasible in such case.

Proposition 2. Consider system (8) with Assumptions 1 to 3, in closed-loop with the control law (12). Then the equilibrium $x = x^*$, with $q = q^*$ and $p = p^* = 0$, is asymptotically stable for all $K_j > 0$ provided that either $(Gk_v G^T + \frac{1}{2}(DM^{-1}M_d) + \frac{1}{2}(DM^{-1}M_d)^T) > 0$, or that $D = 0$ and the output $y = G^T M_d^{-1}p$ is detectable.

Proof. Note first that $W_d = \Omega_d + \frac{1}{2}p^T M_d^{-1}p + \frac{1}{2}\sum_{k=1}^s \zeta_k^T \zeta_k$ is positive definite. Expressing $(DM^{-1}M_d)$ as the sum of a symmetric part Φ_0 and an antisymmetric part Ψ_0 , that is $(DM^{-1}M_d) = \Phi_0 + \Psi_0$, where $\Phi_0 = \frac{1}{2}(DM^{-1}M_d) + \frac{1}{2}(DM^{-1}M_d)^T$ and $\Psi_0 = \frac{1}{2}(DM^{-1}M_d) - \frac{1}{2}(DM^{-1}M_d)^T$, and computing the time derivative of W_d along the trajectories of the closed-loop system (9) while recalling that $J_2 = -J_2^T$ yields

$$\dot{W}_d = -\nabla_p W_d^T (Gk_v G^T + \Phi_0)\nabla_p W_d - \sum_{j=1}^s (\nabla_{x_j} W_d^T K_j \nabla_{x_j} W_d) \leq 0, \tag{20}$$

where $\nabla_p W_d = M_d^{-1}p + \sum_{j=1}^s ((\nabla_p \zeta_j)^T \zeta_j)$, $\nabla_{x_i} W_d = \sum_{j=i}^s ((\nabla_{x_i} \zeta_j)^T \zeta_j)$, and $\nabla_{x_s} W_d = (\nabla_{x_s} \zeta_s)^T \zeta_s$. If $K_j > 0, D \neq 0$ and $(Gk_v G^T + \Phi_0) > 0$ it follows from (20) that $q, p, \zeta_j \in \mathcal{L}^\infty, \forall j$, while $p, \sum_{j=1}^s ((\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j)^T \zeta_j), \zeta_s \in \mathcal{L}^2$. It follows from (10) that $\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j \neq 0$, thus $p, \zeta_j \in \mathcal{L}^2 \cap \mathcal{L}^\infty, \forall j$. Finally, it follows from (9) that $\dot{q}, \dot{p}, \dot{\zeta}_j \in \mathcal{L}^\infty$. Thus ζ_j, p converge to zero asymptotically according to Barbalat's Lemma, and the equilibrium is asymptotically stable [24]. In case $D = 0$, it follows from (20) that $y \in \mathcal{L}^2 \cap \mathcal{L}^\infty$ and from (9) that $\dot{q}, \dot{p} \in \mathcal{L}^\infty$ hence also $\dot{y} \in \mathcal{L}^\infty$, and y converges to zero asymptotically rather than p . Asymptotic stability of the equilibrium is then established in a similar fashion, provided that the output $y = G^T M_d^{-1}p$ is detectable [18].

Substituting $\dot{p} = p = 0$ and $\zeta_j = 0$ in (9) yields $\nabla_q \Omega_d = 0$, thus the equilibrium is an extremum of Ω_d , while $\nabla_q^2 \Omega_d(q^*) > 0$ by design, that is $q^* = \text{argmin}(\Omega_d)$. Substituting $p = 0$ and $\zeta_j = 0$ in (10) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 G^\dagger(-\nabla_q \Omega + \mathcal{F}_{23}\nabla_{x_1}W + M_d M^{-1}\nabla_q \Omega_d) = 0, \\
 - \sum_{j=1}^k \mathcal{F}'_{j+2,k+1}\nabla_{x_j}W + \mathcal{F}'_{1,k+1}\nabla_q \Omega_d = 0, \tag{21}
 \end{aligned}$$

which, computed at $(q, p) = (q^*, 0)$, define the values x_j^* for all $j \geq 1$ at the equilibrium, concluding the proof. \square

4.2. Second controller design

The analytical expression of the control law (12) grows in size and complexity with s , thus potentially resulting in increasing computational load. In an attempt to mitigate this shortcoming, the elements of \mathcal{F}' on the diagonal that refer to the actuator states x_j , with $1 \leq j \leq s$, are defined instead as

$$\mathcal{F}'_{j+2,j+2} = -K_j + \left(\mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2} \nabla_q \zeta_j + \mathcal{F}'_{2,j+2} \nabla_p \zeta_j + \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} \mathcal{F}'_{i+2,j+2} \nabla_{x_i} \zeta_j \right) (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j)^{-1}. \quad (22)$$

The expression of ζ_k for $k > 1$ that ensures matching between (8) and (9) for the states (x_2, \dots, x_s) becomes then

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_k = & -\mathcal{F}'_{1,k+1} \nabla_q W - \mathcal{F}'_{2,k+1} \nabla_p W - \sum_{j=1}^k \mathcal{F}'_{j+2,k+1} \nabla_{x_j} W \\ & + \mathcal{F}'_{1,k+1} \left(\nabla_q H_d + \left(\sum_{i=1}^{k-2} (\nabla_{x_i} \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i \right) \right) \\ & + \mathcal{F}'_{2,k+1} \left(M_d^{-1} p + \left(\sum_{i=1}^{k-2} (\nabla_{x_i} \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i \right) \right) \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^{k-2} \mathcal{F}'_{j+2,k+1} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{k-2} (\nabla_{x_i} \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i \right) + K_{k-1} (\nabla_{x_{k-1}} \zeta_{k-1})^T \zeta_{k-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Note that, differently from (10), ζ_k in (23) only contains ζ_{k-1} in the last term, thus resulting in a shorter expression. Similarly, the control law (12) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} u = & G_0^{-1} \left(\mathcal{F}'_{1,s+2} \nabla_q W + \mathcal{F}'_{2,s+2} \nabla_p W + \sum_{j=1}^s \mathcal{F}'_{j+2,s+2} \nabla_{x_j} W \right) \\ & + G_0^{-1} \left(-\mathcal{F}'_{1,s+2} \left(\nabla_q H_d + \sum_{i=1}^{s-1} (\nabla_{x_i} \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i \right) \right) \\ & - G_0^{-1} \left(\mathcal{F}'_{2,s+2} \left(\nabla_p H_d + \sum_{i=1}^{s-1} (\nabla_{x_i} \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i \right) \right) \\ & + G_0^{-1} \left(+ \sum_{j=1}^{s-1} \mathcal{F}'_{j+2,s+2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{s-1} (\nabla_{x_i} \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i \right) - K_s (\nabla_{x_s} \zeta_s)^T \zeta_s \right). \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

Proposition 3. Consider the system (8) with Assumptions 1 to 3, with the control law (24) and the parameters (23). Then the closed-loop system is given by (9) with the matrix \mathcal{F}' defined in (11) where the diagonal terms are given by (22).

Proof. Equating the first rows in (8) and (9) yields again (13), while equating the second rows yields (14). Equating the third rows in (8) and (9) and substituting $\mathcal{F}'_{3,j+2}$ with $j > 2$ from (11) yields (18). Computing \mathcal{F}'_{33} from (22) as

$$\mathcal{F}'_{33} = -K_1 + (\mathcal{F}'_{13} \nabla_q \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{23} \nabla_p \zeta_1) (\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^{-1},$$

and substituting it in (18) yields

$$\begin{aligned} & -\mathcal{F}'_{23} \nabla_p W + \mathcal{F}'_{33} \nabla_{x_1} W + \mathcal{F}'_{34} \nabla_{x_2} W + \mathcal{F}'_{13} (\nabla_q H_d) + \mathcal{F}'_{23} (M_d^{-1} p) \\ & + K_1 ((\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) = \\ & -\mathcal{F}'_{13} ((\nabla_q \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2) - \mathcal{F}'_{23} ((\nabla_p \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2) + \mathcal{F}'_{33} (\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2 \\ & + \mathcal{F}'_{34} (\nabla_{x_2} \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The terms to the left of the equal correspond to ζ_2 in (23), and substituting \mathcal{F}'_{34} from (11) verifies (25). This same procedure is then repeated for the remaining states. Equating the last

rows in (8) and (9) yields again (19). Substituting $\mathcal{F}'_{s+2,s+2}$ from (22) and computing the control input yields then (24) concluding the proof. \square

Proposition 4. Consider system (8) with Assumptions 1 to 3, in closed-loop with the control law (24) and the parameters (23). Then the equilibrium $x = x^*$, with $q = q^*$ and $p = p^* = 0$, is asymptotically stable for some $K_j > 0$, provided that either $(Gk_v G^T + \frac{1}{2}(DM^{-1}M_d) + \frac{1}{2}(DM^{-1}M_d)^T) > 0$ or that $D = 0$ and the output $y = G^T M_d^{-1} p$ is detectable.

Proof. Expressing $\mathcal{F}'_{j+2,j+2}$ as the sum of a symmetric part Φ_j and an antisymmetric part Ψ_j , that is $-\mathcal{F}'_{j+2,j+2} = K_j + \Phi_j + \Psi_j$, where $\Phi_j = \frac{1}{2}(-\mathcal{F}'_{j+2,j+2} - K_j) + \frac{1}{2}(-\mathcal{F}'_{j+2,j+2} - K_j)^T$ and $\Psi_j = -\frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{F}'_{j+2,j+2}) + \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{F}'_{j+2,j+2})^T$, and computing the time derivative of W_d along the trajectories of the closed-loop system (9) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{W}_d = & -\nabla_p W_d^T (Gk_v G^T + \Phi_0) \nabla_p W_d \\ & - \sum_{j=1}^s (\nabla_{x_j} W_d^T (K_j + \Phi_j) \nabla_{x_j} W_d). \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Thus $\dot{W}_d \leq 0$ and all states are bounded provided that $(Gk_v G^T + \Phi_0) > 0$ and that $K_j + \Phi_j > 0$, where Φ_0 has been defined in Proposition 2 and it follows from (22) that

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_j = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2} \nabla_q \zeta_j + \mathcal{F}'_{2,j+2} \nabla_p \zeta_j + \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} \mathcal{F}'_{i+2,j+2} \nabla_{x_i} \zeta_j \right) (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j)^{-1} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \left(\mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2} \nabla_q \zeta_j + \mathcal{F}'_{2,j+2} \nabla_p \zeta_j + \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} \mathcal{F}'_{i+2,j+2} \nabla_{x_i} \zeta_j \right)^T (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j)^{-T}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows from (23) and Assumption 2 that $\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j \neq 0$, while $(\mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2} \nabla_q \zeta_j + \mathcal{F}'_{2,j+2} \nabla_p \zeta_j + \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} \mathcal{F}'_{i+2,j+2} \nabla_{x_i} \zeta_j)$ is a sum of bounded terms. Thus there exists a sufficiently large K_j that verifies the inequality $K_j + \Phi_j > 0$. The proof is completed by employing the same arguments used in Proposition 2, thus confirming that the equilibrium is asymptotically stable. \square

Remark 3. In principle, it is possible to combine the controller designs (12) and (24) thus resulting in an hybrid implementation. For instance, defining ζ_k as in (10), $\mathcal{F}'_{s+2,s+2}$ as in (22), and the remaining elements of \mathcal{F}' as in (11), yields again (24). This is however a different control law, since ζ_k are given in (10) rather than in (23). The corresponding stability conditions are then a combination of those given in Propositions 2 and 4, that is $K_j > 0$ for $j < s$, and $K_s + \Phi_s > 0$. The potential benefit of such approach is to combine the stronger stability properties of controller (12) (i.e., the weaker requirements on the parameters K_j) with the simpler expression of the control law resulting from (24).

5. Potential energy shaping

In this section, a variation of the controller (12) is proposed for a narrower class of systems in order to investigate whether it is possible to set $\mathcal{F}'_{11} \neq 0$ and what this would imply in terms of stability of the equilibrium. To this end, a further assumption is introduced which restricts the following result to a narrower class of underactuated mechanical systems.

Assumption 4. The inertia matrix M is constant and diagonal, while $G \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ and $\nabla_q^2 \Omega_d > 0$ are both constant, GG^T is diagonal (i.e., G is a standard basis vector), and $GG^T \nabla_q^2 \Omega_d^{-1} \geq 0$. In addition $\nabla_{x_j} E_k = 0$, $\forall j \neq k$ and $D = 0$.

The control law is designed such that the closed-loop dynamics is given by (9) where $W_d = \Omega_d + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^s \zeta_k^T \zeta_k$ is a positive definite storage function, with ζ_k defined as

$$\zeta_k = \begin{cases} M^{-1}p + \Theta \nabla_q \Omega_d, & k = 0 \\ G^\dagger (-\nabla_q W + \mathcal{F}_{23} \nabla_{x_1} W + \mathcal{F}_{12}^T (\nabla_q \Omega_d + (\nabla_q \zeta_0)^T \zeta_0) + Gk_v G^T (\nabla_p \zeta_0)^T \zeta_0), & k = 1 \\ -\mathcal{F}_{2,k+1}^T \nabla_p W - \sum_{j=1}^k \mathcal{F}_{j+2,k+1}^T \nabla_{x_j} W + \mathcal{F}_{1,k+1}^T (\nabla_q \Omega_d + \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (\nabla_q \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i) \\ + \mathcal{F}_{2,k+1}^T (\sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (\nabla_p \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i) + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \mathcal{F}_{j+2,k+1}^T (\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_i)^T \zeta_i), & k > 1. \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

Thus $\nabla_q \zeta_0 = \Theta \nabla_q^2 \Omega_d$ and $\nabla_p \zeta_0 = M^{-1}$ are constant, while $\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_0 = 0$. The elements of \mathcal{F} on or above the diagonal (i.e. \mathcal{F}'_{kj} on row k and column $j \geq k$), are defined as in (11) apart from the terms

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}'_{11} &= -\Theta, \quad \Theta^2 = (k_m G G^T \nabla_q^2 \Omega_d^{-1}), \quad \mathcal{F}'_{12} = (I + \Theta^2 \nabla_q^2 \Omega_d) M, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{22} &= -Gk_v G^T, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2} &= \left(\Theta \nabla_q \zeta_j - \mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_p \zeta_j - \sum_{i=1}^{j-1} (\mathcal{F}'_{1,i+2} \nabla_{x_i} \zeta_j) \right) (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_j)^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where $\Theta^2 = \Theta \Theta$, the parameter $k_m > 0$ is constant, and the control input is given by (12).

Proposition 5. Consider system (8) with Assumptions 1 to 4, with the control law (12), and with the parameters (27) and (28). Then the closed-loop system is given by (9) with the matrix \mathcal{F}' is defined according to (11) and (28).

Proof. Equating the first rows in (8) and (9) yields

$$\begin{aligned} M^{-1}p &= -\Theta \left(\nabla_q \Omega_d + \sum_{k=0}^s (\nabla_q \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k \right) + \mathcal{F}'_{12} \sum_{k=0}^s (\nabla_p \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k \\ &+ \sum_{j=1}^s \left(\mathcal{F}'_{1,j+2} \sum_{k=j}^s (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k \right). \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Defining ζ_0 as in (27) and \mathcal{F}'_{1j} as in (28) verifies (29).

Equating the second rows in (8) and (9) yields

$$\begin{aligned} -\nabla_q \Omega + \mathcal{F}_{23} \nabla_{x_1} W &= \\ -\mathcal{F}_{12}^T \left(\nabla_q \Omega_d + \sum_{k=0}^s (\nabla_q \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k \right) &+ \mathcal{F}'_{22} \sum_{k=0}^s (\nabla_p \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k \\ + \sum_{j=1}^s \left(\mathcal{F}'_{2,j+2} \sum_{k=j}^s (\nabla_{x_j} \zeta_k)^T \zeta_k \right). \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Defining $\mathcal{F}'_{2,j+2}$ with $j > 1$ according to (11) and substituting it in (30) cancels ζ_j for all $j > 1$. Pre-multiplying both sides of (30) by $G^\otimes = (G^\perp G^{\perp T})^{-1} G^\perp$ gives the matching condition

$$\begin{aligned} G^\otimes (-\nabla_q \Omega + \mathcal{F}_{12}^T \nabla_q \Omega_d) &= \\ G^\otimes (-\mathcal{F}_{12}^T (\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{22} (\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 &+ \mathcal{F}'_{23} (\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1), \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where the terms to the left of the equal correspond to the PDE (6). Note that (31) does not contain ζ_0 since $\text{rank}(\Theta^2) = \text{rank}(GG^T)$ hence $G^\perp \Theta \nabla_q^2 \Omega_d \zeta_0 = 0$. Pre-multiplying both sides of (30) by G^\dagger yields

$$\begin{aligned} G^\dagger (-\nabla_q \Omega + \mathcal{F}_{23} \nabla_{x_1} W + \mathcal{F}_{12}^T \nabla_q \Omega_d &+ \mathcal{F}'_{12} (\nabla_q \zeta_0)^T \zeta_0 \\ - \mathcal{F}'_{22} (\nabla_p \zeta_0)^T \zeta_0) &= \\ G^\dagger (-\mathcal{F}_{12}^T (\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{22} (\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 &+ \mathcal{F}'_{23} (\nabla_{x_1} \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1), \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where the first line corresponds to ζ_1 . Thus, defining \mathcal{F}'_{23} according to (11) solves both (31) and (32). The rest of the proof follows closely that of Proposition 1, thus it is omitted for brevity. \square

Proposition 6. Consider system (8) with Assumptions 1 to 4, in closed-loop with the control law (12) and the parameters (27) and (28). Assume in addition that Ω_d is quadratic in q . Then the equilibrium $x = x^*$, with $q = q^*$ and $p = p^* = 0$ is stable and $G^T q$ converges to $G^T q^*$ asymptotically for all $K_j > 0, k_v > 0, k_m > 0$, provided that $\Theta + \Theta^T \geq 0$.

Proof. Recall that $W_d = \Omega_d + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^s \zeta_k^T \zeta_k$ is positive definite. Computing its time derivative along the trajectories of the closed-loop system (9) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{W}_d &= -\frac{1}{2} \nabla_q W_d^T (\Theta + \Theta^T) \nabla_q W_d - \nabla_p W_d^T (Gk_v G^T) \nabla_p W_d \\ &- \sum_{j=1}^s (\nabla_{x_j} W_d^T K_j \nabla_{x_j} W_d), \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where $\nabla_q W_d = \nabla_q \Omega_d + (\Theta \nabla_q^2 \Omega_d)^T \zeta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^s ((\nabla_q \zeta_j)^T \zeta_j)$, $\nabla_p W_d = M^{-1} \zeta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^s ((\nabla_p \zeta_j)^T \zeta_j)$, and $\nabla_{x_i} W_d = \sum_{j=i}^s ((\nabla_{x_i} \zeta_j)^T \zeta_j)$. Employing the same argument used in Proposition 2, it follows from (33) that $\dot{W}_d \leq 0$ for all $k_v > 0, K_j > 0$ and $k_m > 0$, where $(\Theta + \Theta^T) \geq 0$ by hypothesis, thus $q, \zeta_j \in \mathcal{L}^\infty$ for all $j \geq 0$. It follows from (28) that Θ^2 is the product of the rank-deficient positive semidefinite diagonal matrix GG^T and of the full-rank positive definite symmetric matrix $\nabla_q^2 \Omega_d^{-1}$, thus it has the same rank as GG^T . Consequently, $G^T \nabla_q W_d, G^T \nabla_p W_d, \nabla_{x_j} W_d \in \mathcal{L}^2$ and thus $G^T \nabla_q \Omega_d, G^T \zeta_0, \zeta_{j>0} \in \mathcal{L}^2$. Finally, it follows from (9) that $\dot{q}, \dot{p}, \dot{\zeta}_j \in \mathcal{L}^\infty$. Thus $\zeta_{j>0}, G^T \zeta_0$, and $G^T \nabla_q \Omega_d$ are bounded and converge to zero asymptotically. Since Ω_d has a unique minimizer in $q = q^*$ by design and is quadratic in q while G is constant, the fact that $G^T \nabla_q \Omega_d$ converges to zero implies that $G^T q$ converges to $G^T q^*$. Finally, substituting $p = 0$ and $\zeta_j = 0$ in (27) yields again (21) which defines the values x_j^* at the equilibrium. \square

Remark 4. Although the parameters (27) and (28) do not explicitly enforce kinetic energy shaping, \mathcal{F}'_{12} can be interpreted as the product of inertia matrices, that is

$$(I + \Theta^2 \nabla_q^2 \Omega_d) M = M^{-1} M_d.$$

Pre-multiplying both sides of the above equation by M and substituting Θ^2 from (28) yields

$$M_d = M(I + k_m G G^T) M,$$

which is constant and symmetric since it is the product of diagonal matrices, thus the PDE (5) is solved by $J_2 = 0$. The ability to shape the kinetic energy is however limited compared to the standard IDA-PBC control (3), since the parameter k_m only affects the actuated states. Note that the proposed potential shaping design is not feasible in the presence of physical damping, since then the matching Eq. (30) would not be verified. Note also that the detectability condition typically required for the output $y = G^T M_d^{-1} p$ [18] is not present in Proposition 6. However, since Θ is chosen to be rank deficient in order to preserve the PDE (6) (see Proposition 5), its effect on the Lyapunov derivative (33) is limited to the actuated states. As a result, only asymptotic convergence to the equilibrium $G^T q = G^T q^*$ is concluded in Proposition 6. If $k_m = 0$ then $M_d = M$

Fig. 1. Simplified schematic of the Acrobot system with a rotary SEA.

and $\Theta = 0$, thus stability of the equilibrium is only concluded if the output $y = G^T \zeta_0$ is detectable. Substituting ζ_0 from (27) $k_m = 0$ yields $y = G^T M^{-1} p + G^T \Theta \nabla_q \Omega_d = G^T M^{-1} p$, thus recovering the detectability condition in Ortega et al. [18]. In alternative to (28), it would be possible to define $\Theta^2 = k_m^2 G G^T$ which is symmetric positive semidefinite and yields $\Theta = k_m G G^T \geq 0$. As a result, the condition $\Theta + \Theta^T \geq 0$ in Proposition 6 is automatically verified. However computing M_d as above yields $M_d = M(I + k_m G G^T \nabla_q^2 \Omega_d) M$ which is in general not symmetric and thus it does not represent the inertia matrix of any mechanical system.

6. Illustrative examples

The energy shaping controllers outlined in Sections 4 and 5 are demonstrated with three examples, namely an Acrobot system with a rotary series elastic actuator (SEA), a soft continuum manipulator actuated by electroactive polymers (EAP), and a two-mass-spring system actuated by a DC motor.

6.1. Acrobot system with SEA

The Acrobot system [16] is modified by including a rotary series elastic actuator (SEA) consisting of a spring, a damper, and a DC motor, where the effect of the inductance is omitted for simplicity [4]. The Acrobot system consists of an articulated pendulum with a single actuator at the elbow joint q_2 and an unactuated shoulder joint q_1 (see Fig. 1). The open-loop dynamics of the mechanical sub-system is given by (1) with total energy $H = \Omega + \frac{1}{2} p^T M^{-1} p$ where $\Omega = g(c_4 \cos(q_1) + c_5 \cos(q_1 + q_2))$, the input matrix is $G^T = [0 \quad 1]$, while $M = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 + c_2 + 2c_3 \cos(q_2) & c_2 + c_3 \cos(q_2) \\ c_2 + c_3 \cos(q_2) & c_2 \end{bmatrix}$ is the inertia matrix with determinant $\Delta = \det(M) > 0$. The terms c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5 are constant parameters depending on the size of the links, while g is the gravity constant. The control goal is to stabilize the upright position $(q_1, q_2) = (0, 0)$, which is open-loop unstable. The IDA-PBC controller (3) for the Acrobot with direct actuation yields the control law [16]

$$u = \frac{1}{2} \nabla_{q_2} (p^T M^{-1} p) + \nabla_{q_2} \Omega - [k_2 \quad k_3] M^{-1} \nabla_q \Omega_d + \frac{k_v}{\Delta_d} (k_2 p_1 - k_1 p_2),$$

where k_1, k_2, k_3, k_v are tuning parameters, $p = M\dot{q}$, while Ω_d and Δ_d are given in Appendix A. The complete system dynamics described with (8) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_{11} = \mathcal{F}_{13} = \mathcal{F}_{14} = \mathcal{F}_{24} = 0, \quad \mathcal{F}_{12} = I, \quad \mathcal{F}_{34} = \frac{1}{J_e}, \\ \mathcal{R}_{22} = 0, \quad \mathcal{F}_{23} = 0, \quad \mathcal{R}_{33} = 0, \quad \mathcal{R}_{44} = \frac{D_a}{J_e^2}, \quad G_0 = \frac{K_e}{R_d J_e} \end{aligned}$$

where K_e and R_a are the torque constant of the motor and the armature resistance respectively, while D_a is the viscous friction of the SEA. The total energy of the system is $W = H + \frac{1}{2} K_a (q_2 - \theta)^2 + \frac{1}{2} J_e \omega^2$, where K_a is the stiffness of the SEA and J_e is the moment of inertia of the motor. The system states are the position $q = (q_1, q_2)$, the momenta $p = M\dot{q}$, the angular position $x_1 = \theta$ of the SEA, and the angular velocity $x_2 = \omega = \dot{\theta}$ of the SEA. Note that $\mathcal{F}_{23} = 0$ but $\nabla_\theta \mathcal{F}_{12}^T \nabla_q W \neq 0$, thus Assumption 2 is verified. The energy of the mechanical sub-system in closed-loop is $H_d = \Omega_d + \frac{1}{2} p^T M_d^{-1} p$ as in D. Mahindrakar et al. [16], and the total energy of the complete system is $W_d = H_d + \frac{1}{2} \zeta_1^T \zeta_1 + \frac{1}{2} \zeta_2^T \zeta_2$, where it follows from (10) and (22) that

$$\zeta_1 = G^\dagger (-\nabla_q W + \mathcal{F}_{12}^T \nabla_q H_d - \mathcal{F}_{22}^T \nabla_p H_d),$$

$$\zeta_2 = \frac{1}{J_e} \nabla_\omega W + K_1 (\nabla_\theta \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}_{23}^T \nabla_p H_d + \mathcal{F}_{13}^T \nabla_q H_d.$$

The elements of \mathcal{F}' computed as in (11) and (22) are given in Appendix A. The control input computed as in (24) is

$$\begin{aligned} u = & \left(K_e + \frac{R_a D_a}{K_e} \right) \omega + \frac{K_a R_a}{K_e} (\theta - q_2) - \frac{J_e R_a}{K_e} \mathcal{F}_{14}^T (\nabla_q H_d + (\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) \\ & - \frac{J_e R_a}{K_e} \mathcal{F}_{24}^T (\nabla_p H_d + (\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) - \frac{J_e R_a}{K_e} \mathcal{F}_{34}^T ((\nabla_\theta \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) \\ & - K_2 \frac{J_e R_a}{K_e} ((\nabla_\omega \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2), \end{aligned}$$

and it employs the parameters Ω_d, M_d and J_2 , which are the solutions of the PDEs (5) and (6) for the Acrobot system with direct actuation [16].

Numerical simulations have been performed in Matlab using an ODE23 solver with the model parameters $c_1 = 0.23333$; $c_2 = 0.53333$; $c_3 = 0.2$; $c_4 = 0.3$; $c_5 = 0.2$; $g = 9.81$; $R_a = 0.5$; $K_e = 1$; $J_e = 10^{-3}$; $D_a = 1$; $K_a = 10$. The tuning parameters have been chosen empirically as $k_0 = -35$; $k_1 = 0.03386$; $k_2 = 0.1$; $k_3 = 0.59073$; $\mu = -0.6019$; $k_u = 1$; $k_v = 2$; $K_1 = 10^3$; $K_2 = 10^4$. The system response with the controller (24) is shown in Fig. 2: the position reaches the prescribed equilibrium $(q_1, q_2) = (0, 0)$ in a similar fashion to the mechanical system with direct actuation and the IDA-PBC controller (3) (see Fig. 2(a) and (g)). The angular position θ and the angular velocity $\omega = \dot{\theta}$ of the motor are shown in Fig. 2(d) and (e) (no gearbox has been included in the model for simplicity). The control input computed as in (24) corresponds to a voltage (see Fig. 2(c)) thus it is not directly comparable with controller (3). Instead, the motor torque has the same order of magnitude with both controllers (see Fig. 2(f) and (i)).

6.2. Soft continuum manipulator with EAP actuation

The dynamics of a soft continuum manipulator of mass m and length l moving on the horizontal plane and actuated by electroactive polymers (EAP) [15] described with (8) yields the parameters

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}_{11} = \mathcal{F}_{13} = \mathcal{F}_{14} = \mathcal{F}_{24} = 0, \quad \mathcal{F}_{12} = \mathcal{F}_{34} = I, \quad \mathcal{R}_{22} = D, \\ \mathcal{F}_{23} = K_c G, \quad \mathcal{R}_{33} = R_2, \quad \mathcal{R}_{44} = R_1, \quad G_0 = I, \end{aligned}$$

where R_1, R_2 are resistances, and K_c represents the coupling between EAP and soft continuum manipulator. The latter is modeled as a rigid-link system with $n = 2$ virtual elastic joints of stiffness k and damping D [27], where only the first is actuated thus $G^T = [1 \quad 0]$ (see Fig. 3). The total energy of the mechanical sub-system is $H = \Omega + \frac{1}{2} p^T M^{-1} p$, where $\Omega = \frac{1}{2} k (q_1^2 + q_2^2)$ with q_1 and q_2 the angles of the virtual joints, and $M = \frac{m l^2}{4} \begin{bmatrix} 4 \cos(q_2) + 6 & 2 \cos(q_2) + 1 \\ 2 \cos(q_2) + 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$. The total energy of the complete system is $W = H + \frac{1}{2C} Q^2 + \frac{1}{2L} \phi^2$, where C is the capacitance

Fig. 2. Simulation results for the Acrobot with either a SEA or with direct actuation: (a) position with SEA and controller (24); (b) velocity; (c) control input with (24); (d) motor position θ ; (e) motor velocity ω ; (f) motor torque with (24); (g) position with direct actuation and with controller (3); (h) velocity; (i) control input with (3).

Fig. 3. Simplified schematic of the soft continuum manipulator with EAP actuation.

and L is the inductance of the EAP. The system states are the position $q = (q_1, q_2)$, the momenta $p = M\dot{q}$, the electric charge $x_1 =$

Q , and the flux $x_2 = \phi$. The control goal is to stabilize the position $(q_1, q_2) = (q_1^*, 0)$ where, differently from the Acrobot, $q_2 = 0$ is open-loop stable.

The energy of the mechanical sub-system in closed-loop is $H_d = \Omega_d + \frac{1}{2} p^T M_d^{-1} p$, where $M_d = k_m M$ and $\Omega_d = \frac{1}{2} (k_p (q_1 - q_1^*)^2 + \frac{k}{k_m} q_2^2)$ with k_p and k_m tuning parameters, and the control law computed as in (3) is

$$u = kq_1 + k_p k_m (q_1^* - q_1) - \frac{4k_v (p_2 - p_1 + 2p_2 \cos(q_2))}{ml^2 (4 \cos(q_2)^2 - 5)}.$$

Note that setting $M_d = k_m M$ solves the PDE (5) with $J_2 = 0$. The total energy of the complete system in closed loop is $W_d = H_d + \frac{1}{2} \zeta_1^T \zeta_1 + \frac{1}{2} \zeta_2^T \zeta_2$, where it follows from (10) that

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_1 &= G^T (-\nabla_q H + K_c G \nabla_Q W + \mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_q H_d + G k_v G^T \nabla_p H_d), \\ \zeta_2 &= -K_c G^T \nabla_p H - R_2 \nabla_Q W + \nabla_\phi W - \mathcal{F}'_{33} (\nabla_Q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 \\ &\quad + \mathcal{F}'_{23} (\nabla_p H_d + (\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) + \mathcal{F}'_{13} (\nabla_q H_d + (\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1). \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 4. Simulation results for soft continuum manipulator with either EAP actuation or with direct actuation: (a) position with EAP and controller (24); (b) velocity; (c) control input with (24); (d) flux ϕ ; (e) charge Q ; (f) torque with (24); (g) position with direct actuation and with controller (3); (h) velocity; (i) control input with (3).

The elements of \mathcal{F}' computed as in (11) are given in Appendix B. For comparison purposes, ζ_1 and ζ_2 computed as in (23) are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta_1 &= G^\dagger(-\nabla_q H + K_c G \nabla_Q W + \mathcal{F}_{12}^T \nabla_q H_d + G k_\nu G^T \nabla_p H_d), \\ \zeta_2 &= -K_c G^T \nabla_p H - R_2 \nabla_Q W + \nabla_\phi W + K_1 (\nabla_Q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1 \\ &\quad + \mathcal{F}_{23}^T (\nabla_p H_d) + \mathcal{F}_{13}^T (\nabla_q H_d).\end{aligned}$$

Finally, the controller (24) yields

$$\begin{aligned}u &= \frac{Q}{C} + R_1 \frac{\phi}{L} - \mathcal{F}_{14}^T (\nabla_q H_d + (\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) \\ &\quad - \mathcal{F}_{24}^T (\nabla_p H_d + (\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) - \mathcal{F}_{34}^T ((\nabla_Q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) \\ &\quad - K_2 ((\nabla_\phi \zeta_2)^T \zeta_2).\end{aligned}$$

Numerical simulations have been performed in Matlab using an ODE23 solver with the model parameters $m = 1.5$; $l = 0.15$; $k = 1$; $D = 0.15$; $R_1 = 30$; $R_2 = 1.4 \times 10^{-3}$; $K_c = 10^{-3}$; $C = 0.05$; $L = 0.1$. The tuning parameters for the IDA-PBC controller (3) have been chosen empirically as $k_p = 0.75$, $k_m = 2$, and $k_\nu = 0.5$. The tuning parameters for the controller (24) have been chosen as $k_p = 0.75$, $k_m = 2$, $k_\nu = 0.5$, $K_1 = 1$ and $K_2 = 120$ for consistency. The system response with the controller (3) for the mechanical sub-system and with the controller (24) for the complete system is shown in Fig. 4: the position reaches the prescribed equilibrium $(q_1, q_2) = (\pi/6, 0)$ with a similar transient for both controllers applied to the corresponding systems (see Fig. 4(a) and (g)). The flux ϕ and the charge Q corresponding to the EAP are shown in Fig. 4(d) and (e). The control input computed as in (24) corresponds to a voltage (see Fig. 4(c)) and its magnitude (i.e., kV range)

Fig. 5. Simplified schematic of the two-mass-spring system actuated by a DC motor.

is representative of EAP actuators [25]. The resulting torque has the same order of magnitude as the control input computed with (3) for the mechanical sub-system (see Fig. 4(f) and (i)). Note that employing the controller (3), which does not account for EAP actuation, on the complete system (8) yields $q_1 \approx q_2 \approx 0$, thus the regulation goal $(q_1, q_2) = (\pi/6, 0)$ is not achieved (see Appendix B). The hybrid implementation discussed in Remark 3 with the same tuning parameters yields similar results, which have been included in Appendix B for completeness.

6.3. Two-mass-spring system with DC motor

The two-mass-spring system presented in Bastos and Franco [1] is modified here by introducing a DC motor for the actuation, and by removing the damper in order to comply with Assumption 4. The positions of the masses are q_1 and q_2 , and the springs have stiffness k_1 , k_2 , and k_3 (see Fig. 5). The energy

Fig. 6. Simulation results for the two-mass-spring system with either DC motor actuation or with direct actuation: (a) position with DC motor and with controller (12); (b) velocity; (c) control input and corresponding torque with (12); (d) position with DC motor and with controller (3); (e) velocity; (f) control input with (3); (g) position with direct actuation and with controller (3); (h) velocity; (i) control input with (3).

of the mechanical sub-system is $H = \Omega + \frac{1}{2}m_1\dot{q}_1^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_2\dot{q}_2^2$, where $\Omega = \frac{k_1q_1^2}{2} + \frac{k_2(q_2-q_1)^2}{2} + \frac{k_3q_2^2}{2}$, the inertia matrix is $M = \begin{bmatrix} m_1 & 0 \\ 0 & m_2 \end{bmatrix}$, and the input matrix is $G^T = [1 \quad 0]$. The control goal corresponds to moving the second mass to a prescribed position such that $(q_1, q_2) = (q_1^*, q_2^*)$, where q_1^* depends on q_2^* , that is $q_1^* = q_2^* \frac{k_2+k_3}{k_2}$, since the system is underactuated.

Employing the IDA-PBC design (3) yields the control law

$$u = k_1q_1 + k_2(q_1 - q_2) + \frac{a_1m_2(k_2q_2 - k_2q_1 + k_3q_2^*)}{a_3m_1} - \frac{k_v m_1 \dot{q}_1}{a_1},$$

where k_v, a_1, a_3 are tuning parameters, the closed-loop system has constant inertia matrix $M_d = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & 0 \\ 0 & a_3 \end{bmatrix}$, and the potential energy is

$$\Omega_d = \left(\frac{k_2}{2} \left(q_1 + q_2^* - q_2^* \frac{(k_2+k_3)}{k_2} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} q_2^2 (k_2+k_3) - k_2 q_1 q_2 \right) \frac{m_2}{a_3} + \frac{k_3 m_2 q_2^{*2}}{2a_3}.$$

Accounting for the dynamics of a DC motor with negligible inertia that actuates the first mass through a pinion-rack arrangement, the total energy of the system becomes $W = H + \frac{1}{2}L_a I_a^2$, where L_a is the inductance of the motor and I_a is the armature current. The complete system dynamics described with (8) yields

$$\mathcal{F}_{11} = \mathcal{F}_{13} = 0, \quad \mathcal{F}_{12} = I, \quad \mathcal{R}_{22} = 0, \quad \mathcal{F}_{23} = G \frac{K_e}{L_a}, \quad \mathcal{R}_{33} = \frac{R_a}{L_a^2}, \quad G_0 = \frac{1}{L_a},$$

where K_e and R_a are the torque constant of the motor and the armature resistance respectively. The system states are the position $q = (q_1, q_2)$, the momenta $p = M\dot{q}$, and the armature current $x_1 = I_a$. The total energy of the closed-loop system is $W_d = \Omega_d + \frac{1}{2}\zeta_0^T \zeta_0 + \frac{1}{2}\zeta_1^T \zeta_1$, where it follows from (27) that

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta_0 &= M^{-1}p + \Theta \nabla_q \Omega_d, \\ \zeta_1 &= G^\dagger \left(-\nabla_q \Omega + \mathcal{F}'_{12} (\nabla_q \Omega_d + (\nabla_q \zeta_0)^T \zeta_0) \right) \\ &\quad + G^\dagger \left(+ \frac{K_e}{L_a} G \nabla_1 W + G k_v G^T ((\nabla_p \zeta_0)^T \zeta_0) \right). \end{aligned}$$

The elements of \mathcal{F}' computed as in (11) and (28) are given in Appendix C. The controller (12) that achieves potential energy shaping according to Proposition 5 (see Section 5) is

$$\begin{aligned} u &= K_e \dot{q}_1 + R_a I_a - L_a \mathcal{F}'_{13} (\nabla_q H_d + (\nabla_q \zeta_0)^T \zeta_0 + (\nabla_q \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) \\ &\quad - L_a \mathcal{F}'_{23} (\nabla_p H_d + (\nabla_p \zeta_0)^T \zeta_0 + (\nabla_p \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1) - K_1 L_a ((\nabla_{I_a} \zeta_1)^T \zeta_1), \end{aligned}$$

where the potential energy Ω_d is given above with $a_3 = m_2^2$ and $a_1 = (1 + k_m)m_1^2$, and k_m is a tuning parameter.

Numerical simulations have been performed in Matlab using an ODE23 solver with the model parameters $m_1 = 1$; $m_2 = 3$; $k_1 = 5$; $k_2 = 3$; $k_3 = 1$; $R_a = 10$; $K_e = 5$; $L_a = 10^{-2}$. The tuning parameters for the controller (12) corresponding to the complete system have been chosen empirically as $k_m = 0.01$ and $k_v = 2$, while the parameters for the controller (3) corresponding to the mechanical sub-system have been set to $a_1 = (1 + k_m)m_1^2 = 1.01$, $a_3 = m_2^2 = 9$, and $k_v = 2$ for consistency. The system response with both controllers for the corresponding models is shown in Fig. 6: employing the controller (12) for the complete system the position reaches the prescribed equilibrium $(q_1, q_2) = (0.5, 0.67)$ in a smooth fashion (see Fig. 6(a)), and the transient response is similar to that of the mechanical sub-system with the IDA-PBC controller (3) (see Fig. 6(g)). Conversely, employing the controller (3) for the complete system (8) results in a large steady-state error (see Fig. 6(d)), since

in this case the actuator dynamics is not accounted for in the controller design. Comparing Fig. 6(c) and (i) shows that the force produced by the motor is comparable to the control input computed as in (3) for the system with direct actuation.

7. Conclusion

This paper has presented some new results on the energy shaping control for a class of underactuated mechanical systems with high-order actuator dynamics. A controller design procedure which preserves the port-Hamiltonian structure of the closed-loop system and builds upon the IDA-PBC methodology in a modular fashion has been outlined. Two alternative controllers that achieve potential and kinetic energy shaping as well as damping assignment have been detailed. In addition, a variation of the controller design has been discussed for a narrower class of systems, which is characterized by constant and diagonal inertia matrix, resulting in different stability conditions.

The simulation results demonstrate that the proposed controllers effectively achieve the prescribed regulation goal for three different underactuated mechanical systems with corresponding actuator dynamics. In addition, the controllers employ the same potential and kinetic energy shaping and damping assignment as the traditional IDA-PBC for mechanical systems with direct actuation, thus resulting in a similar transient. Conversely, employing the traditional IDA-PBC controller alone, which neglects the actuator dynamics, can result in degraded performance. Future work will aim to relax the initial assumptions and to extend the results to multiple interconnected underactuated mechanical systems.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Enrico Franco: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Alessandro Astolfi:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

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Appendix A

Design parameters of the Acrobot system with direct actuation.

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{q_1} \Omega_d &= -k_0 \sin(q_1 - \mu q_2) - b_1 \sin(q_1) - b_2 \sin(q_1 + q_2) \\ &\quad - b_3 \sin(q_1 + 2q_2) - b_4 \sin(q_1 - q_2) + k_u(q_1 - \mu q_2), \\ \nabla_{q_2} \Omega_d &= k_0 \mu \sin(q_1 - \mu q_2) - b_2 \sin(q_1 + q_2) \\ &\quad - 2b_3 \sin(q_1 + 2q_2) + b_4 \sin(q_1 - q_2) - k_u(q_1 - \mu q_2), \\ M_d &= \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & k_2 \\ k_2 & k_3 \end{bmatrix}, \quad b_1 = \frac{g}{2k_2} (c_3 c_4 \pm 2c_4 \sqrt{c_1 c_2}), \end{aligned}$$

Fig. B1. Simulation results for soft continuum manipulator with EAP actuation using the IDA-PBC controller defined as in (3): (a) position; (b) velocity; (c) control input in [V].

Fig. B2. Simulation results for soft continuum manipulator with EAP actuation using the hybrid implementation discussed in Remark 3: (a) position; (b) velocity; (c) control input; (d) flux ϕ ; (e) charge Q ; (f) torque.

$$b_2 = \frac{g\mu}{2k_2(\mu+1)}(c_3c_4 \pm 2c_5\sqrt{c_1c_2}),$$

$$b_3 = \frac{g\mu c_3c_5}{2k_2(\mu+2)}, \quad b_4 = \frac{g\mu c_3c_4}{2k_2(\mu-1)}, \quad \Delta_d = k_1k_3 - k_2^2.$$

Elements of \mathcal{F}' computed as in (11) and (22) for the Acrobot system with rotary SEA.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}'_{12} &= M^{-1}M_d, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{13} = -(\mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_p\zeta_1)(\nabla_\theta\zeta_1)^{-1}, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{14} &= -(\mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_p\zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{13}\nabla_\theta\zeta_2)(\nabla_\omega\zeta_2)^{-1}, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{22} = -Gk_vG^T, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{23} &= G(1 + G^\dagger\mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_q\zeta_1 - G^\dagger\mathcal{F}'_{22}\nabla_p\zeta_1)(\nabla_\theta\zeta_1)^{-1} \\ &\quad + G^{\perp T}(G^\otimes\mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_q\zeta_1 - G^\otimes\mathcal{F}'_{22}\nabla_p\zeta_1)(\nabla_\theta\zeta_1)^{-1}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}'_{24} &= (\mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_q\zeta_2 - \mathcal{F}'_{22}\nabla_p\zeta_2 - \mathcal{F}'_{23}\nabla_\theta\zeta_2)(\nabla_\omega\zeta_2)^{-1}, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{34} &= (1 + \mathcal{F}'_{13}\nabla_q\zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{23}\nabla_p\zeta_2 - \mathcal{F}'_{33}\nabla_\theta\zeta_2)(\nabla_\omega\zeta_2)^{-1}, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{33} &= -K_1 + (\mathcal{F}'_{13}\nabla_q\zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{23}\nabla_p\zeta_1)(\nabla_\theta\zeta_1)^{-1}, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{44} &= -K_2 + (\mathcal{F}'_{14}\nabla_q\zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{24}\nabla_p\zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{34}\nabla_\theta\zeta_2)(\nabla_\omega\zeta_2)^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Appendix B

Elements of \mathcal{F}' computed as in (11) for the soft continuum manipulator with EAP actuation.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}'_{22} &= -k_mD - Gk_vG^T, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{13} = -(\mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_p\zeta_1)(\nabla_\theta\zeta_1)^{-1}, \\ \mathcal{F}'_{14} &= -(\mathcal{F}'_{12}\nabla_p\zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{13}\nabla_\theta\zeta_2)(\nabla_\phi\zeta_2)^{-1}, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{33} = -K_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_{44} = -K_2, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{23} = G(1 + G^\dagger \mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_q \zeta_1 - G^\dagger \mathcal{F}'_{22} \nabla_p \zeta_1)(\nabla_Q \zeta_1)^{-1} \\ + G^{\perp T} (G^\otimes \mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_q \zeta_1 - G^\otimes \mathcal{F}'_{22} \nabla_p \zeta_1)(\nabla_Q \zeta_1)^{-1},$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_{24} = (\mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_q \zeta_2 - \mathcal{F}'_{22} \nabla_p \zeta_2 - \mathcal{F}'_{23} \nabla_Q \zeta_2)(\nabla_\phi \zeta_2)^{-1},$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_{34} = (1 + \mathcal{F}'_{13} \nabla_q \zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{23} \nabla_p \zeta_2 - \mathcal{F}'_{33} \nabla_Q \zeta_2)(\nabla_\phi \zeta_2)^{-1}.$$

Elements on the diagonal of \mathcal{F}' defined as in (22).

$$\mathcal{F}'_{33} = -K_1 + (\mathcal{F}'_{13} \nabla_q \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{23} \nabla_p \zeta_1)(\nabla_Q \zeta_1)^{-1},$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_{44} = -K_2 + (\mathcal{F}'_{14} \nabla_q \zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{24} \nabla_p \zeta_2 + \mathcal{F}'_{34} \nabla_Q \zeta_2)(\nabla_\phi \zeta_2)^{-1}.$$

Simulation results for the soft continuum manipulator with EAP actuation using the IDA-PBC controller (3) are shown in Fig. B1. Note that the position does not reach the prescribed value $(q_1, q_2) = (\pi/6, 0)$ since the control input (i.e., in Volt) is insufficient to activate the EAP.

Simulation results for the soft continuum manipulator with EAP actuation using the hybrid implementation discussed in Remark 3 are shown in Fig. B2: ζ_1, ζ_2 are defined as in (10), \mathcal{F}'_{44} as in (22), and the remaining elements of \mathcal{F}' as in (11). For consistency, the tuning parameters are the same as those employed in Section 6.2.

Appendix C

Elements of \mathcal{F}' computed as in (11) and (28) for the two-mass-spring system with DC motor actuation.

$$\Theta^2 = k_m G G^T (\nabla_q^2 \Omega_d), \quad \mathcal{F}'_{12} = (I + k_m G G^T) M, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{22} = -G k_v G^T,$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_{13} = (-\mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_p \zeta_1 + \mathcal{F}'_{11} \nabla_q \zeta_1)(\nabla_{I_a} \zeta_1)^{-1},$$

$$\mathcal{F}'_{23} = G(1 + G^\dagger \mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_q \zeta_1 - G^\dagger \mathcal{F}'_{22} \nabla_p \zeta_1)(\nabla_{I_a} \zeta_1)^{-1} \\ + G^{\perp T} (G^\otimes \mathcal{F}'_{12} \nabla_q \zeta_1 - G^\otimes \mathcal{F}'_{22} \nabla_p \zeta_1)(\nabla_{I_a} \zeta_1)^{-1}, \quad \mathcal{F}'_{33} = -K_1.$$

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